

THE EFFECT OF BOARD GENDER DIVERSITY ON FIRM PERFORMANCE IN GHANA

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of gender diversity on firm performance, proxied by return on equity. This study also examined the moderating effects of ownership concentration and firm size in the relationship between gender diversity and return on equity. Using a sample of ten manufacturing companies listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE) over the period of 2014 to 2023, this study found that gender diversity has a positive, albeit statistically insignificant, effect on ROE. Furthermore, neither ownership concentration nor firm size significantly moderates the relationship between gender diversity and ROE for firms listed on the GSE. These results contest existing literature, highlighting the need for further research to understand under what conditions gender diversity influences financial outcomes such as return on assets (ROA) and ROE. The study recommends that management and regulatory bodies adopt the critical mass theory to harness the potential benefits of female board representation for corporate performance. Firms should establish specific targets to ensure a minimum number of women on their boards, with these targets informed by empirical research on critical mass thresholds. This study contributes originality by being the first to explore how ownership concentration and firm size interact with gender diversity to influence firm performance.

Keywords: Gender diversity, Return on equity, Critical mass theory, corporate governance

1. Introduction

Corporate boards are essential in determining organizational strategy and ensuring effective governance, as they support managerial decisions with stakeholder interests. Board characteristics including diversity, qualifications, experience, share ownership, and compensation, significantly influence their effectiveness. Amongst these characteristics, board gender diversity (BGD) has received increasing academic attention due to its possibility to improve cognitive diversity, decision quality, and firm performance (Campbell & Minguez-Vera, 2008; Fondas, 2000). Gender-diverse boards are theorized to foster more comprehensive deliberations, improve oversight, and integrate a wider range of stakeholder perspectives.

Empirical evidence on the link between BGD and firm performance (FP), however, remains inconclusive. Studies such as Liu et al. (2014) and Marinova et al. (2016) report that female representation on boards is positively associated with financial performance, particularly when women hold executive positions. Conversely, other research documents weak, negative, or non-linear relationships, suggesting that excessive diversity may yield diminishing returns or reflect tokenism (Rose, 2007; Sarpong-Danquah, 2023; Wang et al., 2024; Xie et al., 2024). These mixed findings indicate that the BGD–FP relationship is likely contingent on firm-specific factors. Prior studies have highlighted the moderating roles of ownership concentration and firm size, as concentrated ownership may strengthen board accountability (Hammouda, 2022), while firm size can influence the extent to which diversity translates into performance outcomes (Mohsni & Shata, 2021).

Despite widely research done in developed economies, evidence from emerging markets remains scarce. In Ghana, the government has implemented initiatives, such as the Affirmative Action Plan, to enhance female participation in corporate leadership. Nevertheless, women remain understated on boards, and the extent to which gender diversity contributes to firm performance—particularly in manufacturing firms—remains unclear. Manufacturing firms are a critical driver of Ghana’s employment and economic growth, yet many face persistent financial underperformance. Understanding whether board gender diversity enhances their financial performance, and how ownership concentration and firm size shapes this relationship, is both theoretically and practically pertinent.

This study addresses this gap by examining the effect of board gender diversity on the financial performance of manufacturing firms listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE) from 2014 to 2023. Return on equity (ROE) is used as the primary performance indicator, reflecting the efficiency with which firms utilize shareholder funds. Furthermore, the study investigates whether ownership concentration and firm size moderate the board gender diversity and firm performance relationship. By providing evidence from a Sub-Saharan African context, this research extends the corporate governance literature, addressing the scarcity of evidence in the developing countries. Also, this study offers practical implications for policymakers and corporate leaders seeking to optimize board composition for sustainable value creation. By combining insights from board composition, ownership structure, and firm characteristics, this study provides a nuanced understanding of how gender diversity can be leveraged to enhance shareholder value in emerging markets.

The study is organized into five sections. Section two reviews literature on BGD and FP. Section three outlines the research methodology, focusing on research strategy and design. Section four presents and discusses the findings, while section five, the final chapter, addresses the study’s findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

A board that includes both male and female directors is referred to as a gender-diverse board, which brings together a range of experiences, skills, and knowledge (Salma and Qian, 2021). The subject of GD on board is increasingly recognized as crucial worldwide (Aguir et al., 2023). Various countries are enacting corporate governance reforms aimed specifically at enhancing gender diversity within their boards (Kompa & Witkowska, 2018). Galbreath (2018) has extensively discussed board gender diversity, emphasizing its significance not only for corporate governance but also for reflecting women's roles in various economic activities. Though having varied genders on the board can contribute valuable skill and knowledge that may improve organizational performance, it can also result in inefficiencies (Boutchkova et al., 2021). Diversity entails varying perspectives (Saeed & Sameer, 2017), and it is anticipated that gender diversity will enhance decision-making through this multiplicity of viewpoints. Research by Tleubayev et al. (2020) indicates that men and women have differing attitudes toward risk and opportunity. Qualities often associated with success in high-level places, like decisiveness and leadership, are traditionally linked to men rather than women (Heilman et al., 1989). Consequently, women are frequently perceived as lacking the necessary traits for success in male-dominated fields, leading to stereotypes that can impede their advancement to top management roles. Generally, it is believed that men are more competitive, self-assured, and courageous in confronting risks (Poletti-Hughes & Briano-Turrent, 2019). However, this perspective is contradicted by findings from Sila et al. (2016), who assert that boards with a greater percentage of women do not engage in more or fewer risk-taking decisions than male-majority boards. This raises questions about whether gender-balanced management should guarantee equal opportunities for both genders and equitable risk-taking behavior. Evidence suggests that women excel in product diversification and communication responsibilities (Ain et al., 2020).

It is projected that when we have more women on the board, it will mitigate agency problems (Ain et al., 2020). Shareholders often emphasize the importance of female board representation, believing that women can better appreciate the desires and prospects of stakeholders (Aguir et al., 2023). Women typically demonstrate higher caution and a tendency toward risk aversion. This cautiousness may increase the likelihood of dividend distribution, as female directors are likely to demand greater oversight from the management team and tend to make decisions that favor shareholders. However, their risk-averse nature might affect their choices in approving decisions concerning the company's welfare. Huang and Kisgen (2013) noted that female directors may be less adept at managing debt. According to Ngo et al. (2019), female directors often exhibit less boldness when investing in uncertain markets, which can result in reduced cash expenditures, such as lower dividend payouts, and a tendency to retain cash during these periods. Such uncertain market conditions are frequently observed in rapidly growing economies. Conversely, women have advantages in developing communication channels that align with external stakeholders, aiding in the resolution of agency problems and facilitating access to resources (Khan et al., 2023).

Findings from psychology and experimental economics indicate that women generally display risk aversion in their investment choices (Charness & Gneezy, 2012). Behavioral finance supports this, providing substantial evidence that women are more risk-averse than men when making decisions regarding investment and finance (Barber & Odean, 2001; Halko et al., 2012). Kamas and Preston (2012) attributed these differences to varying confidence levels that affect the competitiveness of females compared to males. Miller and Ubeda (2012) indicated that

women are extra delicate to the context of decision-making. Alternative explanation is that women, being more budget-constrained, tend to monitor their finances more closely than men, often cutting expenditures while men focus on increasing earnings (OECD, 2013). Croson and Gneezy (2009) settled that variations in confidence, emotional reactions to risk, and perceptions of uncertainty are significant factors influencing gender differences in risk-taking behavior.

In GCC countries, female representation on boards remains low, likely due to cultural, socioeconomic, or religious factors (Bayanpourtehrani and Sylwester, 2013). Despite their high educational qualifications, cultural perceptions often hinder women's access to boardrooms and influential decision-making roles. Adams and Ferreira (2004) noted that companies in riskier settings tend to have more homogeneous boards, while De Cabo et al. (2009) found that banks that have lower risk tend to have a greater percentage of women on their boards. Fondas and Sasselos (2000) attributed this trend to enhanced managerial control leading to improved bank performance with increased female board representation.

Universally, there is growing awareness in boosting female involvement on corporate boards, as research indicates that GD has a substantial effect on CG mechanisms, financial reporting, and corporate financial policies (Salma and Qian, 2021). GD on boards is typically understood as the ratio of male to female board members (Salma & Qian, 2021). Previous research highlights significant benefits connected with the existence of female directors on corporate boards. Additionally, both mandatory and self-regulatory measures regarding gender diversity have proven effective in increasing women's representation on corporate boards across various countries. Shimeld et al. (2017) and Adams and Kirchmaier (2016) argue that gender diversity regulations are the most effective means of increasing the number of female directors on corporate boards. Studies on gender diversity have advanced from sociology and psychology into business literature, demonstrating that GD positively influences management and business strategy, making female directors critical to organizational performance (Salma & Qian, 2021). Research on GD in corporate boards is multidisciplinary, integrating theoretical perspectives from sociology, psychology, accounting, finance, corporate governance, and corporate social responsibility (CSR). Recent studies of 120 Norwegian firms indicate that women's professional backgrounds and values significantly impact strategic and board decision-making processes (Nielsen & Huse, 2010). Furthermore, a firm's financial decisions—such as mergers and acquisitions, strategic alliances, diversification, innovation, investment, and divestment—are sensitive to the presence of women on the board (Bennouri et al., 2018). Studies have connected gender-diverse boards to lower earnings quality (Lara et al., 2017) and higher ROA and ROE (Bennouri et al., 2018). The existence of female directors also significantly leads to maintaining the quality of a business financial record. Additionally, literature on BGD suggests that female directors create value for relevant stakeholders, including shareholders and users of financial information. Ultimately, GD promotes socially responsible behavior in firms, benefiting employees, communities, and societal contributions (Bernardi and Threadgill, 2010).

2.2 The Impact of Board Gender Diversity on Firm Performance

The board of directors serves as a crucial mechanism within a company, tasked with leading and directing the firm while safeguarding the interests of shareholders (Abdullah, 2004). Explicitly, the board performs numerous key roles, including evaluating the suitability of corporate strategies (Abdullah, 2004; He & Huang, 2011), overseeing and directing managers (Abdullah, 2004; O'Connell & Cramer, 2010), appointing and supervising senior management, and linking the corporation to its external environment (Campbell & Mínguez-Vera, 2008).

These roles establish the board as a vital internal control mechanism for corporate governance (Campbell & Mínguez-Vera, 2008). Recent financial scandals, high company failure rates, and the 2008 financial crisis have raised significant concerns regarding the effectiveness of boards (Reguera-Alvarado et al., 2015). In this context, BD has been proposed as a means to enhance efficiency. Erhardt et al. (2003) classify diversity into two categories: demographic and cognitive. As the female workforce increases, companies are witnessing a transformation in their potential candidate pool (Erhardt et al., 2003).

Since boards of directors reflect workforce diversity (Mahadeo et al., 2012), this modification influences board structure. Good corporate governance focuses on developing practices that ensure corporate management accountability and enhance firm performance (Brammer et al., 2007). BGD is a significant governance issue and is regarded as essential for efficient CG (Gallego-Álvarez et al., 2010). Debates about the gender structure of boards typically revolve around moral and financial concerns (Campbell & Mínguez-Vera, 2008; Martin et al., 2008). The ethical view highlights the under-representation of women in boardrooms as discriminatory, arguing it is unethical to exclude female directors based solely on gender (Brammer et al., 2007; Campbell & Mínguez-Vera, 2008). In contrast, economic opinions suggest that such discrimination is inefficient rather than immoral (Brammer et al., 2007).

Prior studies support the notion that female directors positively impact FP for several reasons. First, diverse directors can boost productivity and company value by contributing unique traits, skills, and capacities to the board (Carter et al., 2008). Second, gender diversity enhances problem-solving capabilities by introducing various perspectives into board discussions (Burke, 1994; Rose, 2007; Campbell & Mínguez-Vera, 2008). Different viewpoints can provide substitutes for decision-makers, leading to more thorough deliberations (Carter et al., 2003). Moreover, BD fosters a better understanding of the marketplace, which is increasingly diverse (Carter et al., 2003). Gender-diverse boards indicate that a firm is equipped to comprehend the business landscape and cater to a varied market (Miller and Triana, 2009). Female directors are better positioned to connect their companies with female customers, employees, and community members due to their distinct experiences and viewpoints (Liu et al., 2013).

Some studies report a positive correlation (Carter et al., 2003; Erhardt et al., 2003), while others indicate a negative correlation (Shrader et al., 1997), and some find no significant correlation (Dwyer et al., 2003; Miller and Triana, 2009). For example, Andoh et al. (2023) found that for both non-financial firms and banks, board size is seen to have a significant non-linear impact on Tobin's q . Also, the proportion of foreign board members shows a positively significant relationship with firm performance for both listed non-financial firms and banks. Also, Xie et al. (2024) investigated the impact of board gender diversity on financial performance and how shareholder activism affects the dynamic relationship in the United States. The study found that the relation between board gender diversity and firm performance presents an inverted U-shaped nonlinear form. Firm performance increases as the board are more gender-diverse, but performance decreases after the board diversity level reaches a turning point.

Moreover, Joecks et al. (2013) investigated whether the relationship between GD and FP follows a U-shape based on critical mass theory, using a hand-collected panel dataset from 151 listed German firms between 2000 and 2005. Their evidence indicated a U-shaped relationship, suggesting that a critical mass of women on boards is necessary to fully realize the benefits of diversity. Specifically, they hypothesized that gender diversity would only enhance

performance when female representation exceeds 10%, and that efficiency would surpass that of all-male boards when female representation reaches 30% or more (three or more women). Liu et al. (2014) studied the association between BGD and FP among China's listed firms from 1999 to 2011. Their results showed a positive and significant link, with female executive directors exerting a stronger positive effect on performance than female independent directors, suggesting that the executive role has a more substantial impact than the monitoring function.

Again, Kç and Kuzey (2016) examined the effect of BGD on performance in Turkish listed companies and found that while males predominantly occupy boards, the presence of female directors positively impacts financial performance, measured through return on assets, equity, and sales. The authors concluded that female directors boost performance by bringing diverse perspectives to discussions and projecting a positive image to stakeholders. In their research, Smith, Smith, and Verner (2006) reaffirmed the positive effects of women in top management on firm performance, underscoring that these benefits are influenced by the qualifications of female leaders.

Brahma et al. (2021) confirmed that gender diversity has a positive and significant effect on financial performance, particularly when three or more women serve on boards. They also highlighted that women in executive positions, along with their age and education level, significantly contribute to performance post-appointment. Erhardt et al. (2003) explored BD and firm FP, revealing a positive association between executive diversity and both return on investment and return on assets. Their study suggested that diverse boards contribute positively to overall organizational performance.

The existence of women on the board contributes many standpoints, skills, and know-how that can augment decision-making (Ben Slama et al., 2019). This variety of standpoints permits boards to make further thoughtful and state-of-the-art decisions. Numerous studies have demonstrated that organizations with gender-diverse boards often achieve better financial performance (Pandey et al., 2022). Additionally, female board members are associated with improved risk management, more innovative interventions, and decision-making that is receptive to market fluctuations and buyer requests (Singh et al., 2023; Maji & Saha, 2021). Thus, promoting GD on boards is not only about achieving fair representation but also serves as a strategic investment that can enhance a company's performance, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability in a rapidly evolving business environment (Darmawan, 2024).

However, Sarpong-Danquah (2023) focused on the impact of board gender diversity on the financial performance of firms is not known. This study engages data from 408 microfinance institutions (MFIs) covering the period 2010–2018 from the six microfinance regions to investigate this impact using the Least Squares Dummy Variable (LSDV) and the System Generalized Method of Moments (SYS-GMM) estimation techniques. The study found that board gender diversity exhibits a strong negative effect on the financial performance of MFIs. The study also observes that the effect of board gender diversity on the financial performance of MFIs escalates in the presence of judicial inefficiency.

Also, Mensah and Onumah (2023) considered the essential role that “female directors” on boards of companies in sub-Saharan Africa play towards corporate financial performance enhancement. The study's sample comprises 105 companies listed on the respective stock markets of nine sub-Saharan African countries. The data are collected from annual reports over

the period 2007–2019, a total of 1,166 firm-year observations. Panel data models are used in the analyses. The study found that the performance effect of earnings management is contingent on-board diversity and this finding persists even after controlling for dynamic endogeneity, simultaneity and unobserved time-invariant heterogeneity inherent in the EM and performance relationship.

Moreover, Wang et al, (2024) employed 1990 publicly listed Japanese companies from 2006 to 2023 and examines the effect of board gender diversity on firm performance in Japan. Findings from the fixed-effects regression model revealed a significant negative impact of board gender diversity on firm performance. This adverse correlation is more pronounced in smaller firms, those with greater leverage and reduced institutional ownership, and regulated and consumer-focused industries, particularly pre-COVID-19. The detrimental impact of board gender diversity on firm performance is transmitted via corporate social responsibility and firm innovation instead of board independence or CEO duality.

Furthermore, Zhang et al., (2024) investigated the effects of board gender diversity on corporate performance, using data from Chinese listed companies spanning the period 2011 to 2020. The study found that a higher number female executive board is associated with a decline in internal corporate performance. Conversely, an increase in the proportion of female executives generally correlates with an improvement in external corporate performance. Moreover, our analysis indicates no significant impact of gender diversity on financial performance. Lefley and Janeček (2024) focused on board gender diversity and critical masses and the study argued that as gender-diverse boards evolve, women will not just be seen as female directors but will be accepted on equal terms with their male counterparts and have an equal voice; gender will no longer be an issue and critical mass theory may then become irrelevant.

Again, Ahmed and Hussain (2024) focused on the dynamics of Australian boards by focusing on the influence of board gender diversity on firms' cash holdings, within the distinctive Australian “if not, why not” regulatory framework. The study used ordinary least squares (OLS), fixed effects, generalized method of moments (GMM) and quasi-experimental methods such as difference-in-differences and propensity score matching to analyze the data. The study found a significantly negative relationship between board gender diversity and corporate cash holdings. This relationship is more pronounced when two or more female directors are on the board, supporting the critical mass theory. The results also reveal that the observed pattern can be attributed to the heightened monitoring intensity of female independent directors.

In their research on “GD in the Boardroom and Firm's Financial Performance”, Campbell and Minguez (2008) assessed the impact of female board members on firm performance. They analyzed various actions of female board representation, including the existence of female directors, their percentage on the board, and catalogs of GD (the Blau and Shannon indices). Their results specified that while the mere existence of women on the board does not affect firm value, a greater diversity of female representation does positively influence it. This suggests that Spanish companies should prioritize achieving a balance rather than just increasing female representation.

Marinova et al. (2016) examined GD and FP in the Netherlands and Denmark, utilizing two-stage least squares estimation with Tobin's Q as a performance measure. Their outcomes showed no effect of BGD on performance, echoing Rose's (2007) conclusions that board

composition in terms of gender does not influence firm performance. Rose argued for the importance of diversity for reasons beyond financial performance, suggesting that corporate boards should reflect broader societal diversity. The benefits of having women in leadership roles were found to strongly depend on their qualifications. Also, Carter et al. (2010) revealed no significant relationship between board gender or ethnic diversity and financial performance among major U.S. corporations. They suggested that BD and FP may be endogenous. Vieito (2013) found that the gender of the CEO has no significant impact on firm performance, risk levels, or stock returns, regardless of whether a firm is classified as high or low risk.

Perryman et al. (2016) noted that firms with greater GD in top management demonstrate lower risk and improved performance. However, even among top management, female executives receive lower compensation than their male counterparts. As gender diversity increases, the pay gap narrows, indicating that companies perceive the enhancement of female executive representation as both a societal necessity and a business advantage. Adams and Ferreira (2009) reported that female directors significantly influence board discussions and firm outcomes. Their research indicated that while boards with more women perform well in monitoring firms, they also identified negative effects of female board members on Tobin's Q and return on assets, leading to an average negative impact of GD on FP, attributed to firms with fewer takeover defenses. Overall, the empirical literature offers limited insights into the effects of BGD on FP in Ghana. This study aims to fill this gap, contributing to the existing body of research on BGD and FP.

2.3 Factors Influencing Board Gender Diversity

Culture is a multifaceted notion that encompasses a wide range of definitions and can include various aspects within an organization (Iivari & Ivari, 2011). According to Ibarra, Ely, and Kolb (2013), four main cultural dimensions tend to favor men: beliefs about gender, office structures, norms, and interaction trends. They argue that “second-generation” gender biases primarily contribute to women's under-representation in leadership roles. These biases create subtle yet powerful barriers that disadvantage women while benefiting men (Ibarra et al., 2013). A prevalent assumption is that men are inherently better leaders, leading to the notion that women are unsuitable for leadership positions (Beeson & Valerio, 2012; Gallant, 2014). This belief is rooted in societal stereotypes that attribute certain leadership traits primarily to men (Hofmeyr & Mzobe, 2012). Research by Eagly and Carli (2007) shows that distinct traits are often associated with women and men, with men more frequently displaying traits linked to leadership. These traits can be divided into two categories: communal (associated with women, such as kindness and empathy) and agentic (associated with men, such as assertiveness and ambition) (Eagly & Carli, 2007). The belief that men make superior leaders can undermine support for female leaders, who may be held to higher standards than their male counterparts and must continually demonstrate their leadership capabilities (Evans, 2011). Toh and Leonardelli (2012) found that women sometimes defer to men in leadership roles, even when exhibiting superior leadership behaviors, due to the perception that masculine traits are more indicative of effective leadership.

Women who do adopt male leadership traits may find themselves in a double bind. While they may be perceived as competent when displaying traditionally valued behaviors like assertiveness, they may simultaneously struggle with popularity (Gallant, 2014; Evans, 2011). The dominant leadership styles within organizations can significantly impact advancement opportunities, with many women believing that these styles are misaligned with their own

leadership and communication approaches (McKinsey, 2013). The Women Matter 2013 survey indicated that nearly 40% of women felt that predominant leadership styles were incompatible with their own. Organizational structures and systems exacerbate the challenges women face in advancing their careers, often favoring men by overlooking women's dual roles (Hofmeyr & Mzobe, 2012). Success in many organizations is still linked to long hours and unwavering commitment, which can be particularly challenging for women balancing family responsibilities (Clarke, 2011). Despite diversity initiatives, few organizations offer substantial support to women during critical periods such as maternity leave (Sandler, 2014). Ely, Ibarra, and Kolb (2011) illustrate this point by highlighting how men often receive better support for demanding careers, such as expatriation arrangements that assume a trailing spouse. This reinforces the belief that men are more suited for leadership roles, as these roles are frequently designed with men in mind (Ely, Ibarra, & Kolb, 2011). McKinsey (2013) also identified a corporate culture characterized by an "anytime, anywhere performance model" as a factor that affects GD, noting that perceptions of flexible work measures as incompatible with top-level careers hinder advancement, particularly for parents of young children.

Leadership commitment is essential for addressing change and overcoming challenges within organizations. The extent to which organizational leaders recognize the tactical relevance of their workforce is crucial for endorsing and implementing diversity practices (Herdman & McMillan-Capehart, 2010). Various external factors, including firm size, board composition, industry type, ownership structure, buyer demographics, and social and cultural features, also affect GD on corporate boards. Brammer, Millington, and Pavelin (2007) emphasize the significance of a firm's external environment and client base in understanding BGD. Their analysis of 243 firms listed on the LSE revealed significant variations in GD across sectors, with greater female representation in industries like retail, utilities, media, and banking, which cater to end consumers. Similarly, Hillman, Shropshire, and Cannella (2007) found that larger firms in the U.S. are likely to have women directors on their boards, and that a firm's probability of female representation increases when it partners with other firms that have women directors.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

2.4.1 Resource Dependence Theory

Four phases characterize the evolution of resource dependence research in organization theory: "(1) the formation phase of the 1950s and 1960s; (2) the heydays of the 1970s and early 1980s; (3) a subsequent phase of stagnation from the mid-1980s to the early 2000s; and (4) the current phase of theory revival, refinement, and interdisciplinary application" (Biermann & Harsch, 2017). In the formation era, researchers found difficulty with the fundamentals of RDT, particularly the factors of changing levels of dependence in resource exchange (Hillman et al., 2009). Sociology, social psychology, social anthropology, and management literature all intersect to form the intellectual roots of RDT (Hillman et al., 2009).

The foundational concept of RDT is rooted in SET, which was formulated by Levine and White (1961), Emerson (1972), and Blau (1964) during the early 1960s. This theory emphasizes the role of reciprocity in influencing social exchanges amongst individuals. The second major component of RDT is derived from management literature, originating from Selznick's (1949) seminal research on the TVA. Subsequently, Pfeffer and Salancik (1974) integrated and broadened insights from both social exchange theory and management literature in their work. Following the release of their influential work, "The External Control", there was a period of widespread acceptance, marked by frequent citations yet minimal attempts to refine the theory

(Oliver, 1991). From the mid-1980s until the early 2000s, progress in theory development was stagnant. However, with the introduction of the second edition of their book in 2003, Pfeffer expressed concern that the fundamental ideas of RDT were often treated as merely "metaphorical statements" rather than being rigorously explored and tested. This critique sparked a resurgence in RDT research (Katila et al., 2008).

RDT begins with the assertion that organizations, situated within their surroundings, rest on external resources for their functionality and survival (Biermann and Harsch, 2017). The environment of an organization encompasses all structures, players, and events that impact its reliance on external resources. RDT views companies as open systems (Hatch, 1997), highlighting their relational nature (Scott, 2003), where resources sourced from or provided to the environment are vital for the system's operation. This open systems perspective stands in contrast to the earlier belief that businesses were closed, self-sufficient bodies, which dominated management studies until the late 1950s.

The organizational setting presents opportunities to obtain essential resources, including facilities, raw materials, capital, equipment, and personnel (Barney, 1991). Potential exchange partners may include sellers, clients, competitors, associations, regulatory bodies, and interest groups. RDT posits that organizations can alter their environment to mitigate their resource dependence, with Aldrich and Pfeffer (1976) suggesting that organizations exercise significant choice and discretion. Nonetheless, companies are not ever completely in control of their setting and the circumstances necessary for achieving efficiency and persistence (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003). RDT principally focuses on how businesses manage or adapt to external challenges. Pfeffer and Salancik (2003) often refer to limitations on corporate independence as the counterpoint to dependence. The uncertainty regarding environmental demands and organizational autonomy remains a significant concern for organizations (Oliver, 1991; Biermann, 2008; Harsch, 2015).

Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) asserts that reliance on external resources imposes limitations on organizational autonomy (Biermann & Harsch, 2017). Recent developments in RDT emphasize the significance of examining both the level and balance of dependence. Two main factors influence the level of resource dependence: the perceived significance of external resources and the accessibility of substitute traders (Levine and White, 1961; Emerson, 1962; Blau, 1964; Jacobs, 1974).

The fundamental tenets of RDT have become almost axiomatic within organization theory (Hillman et al., 2009), although critics have primarily focused on questioning the theory's validity. Only in recent times have scholars begun to refine the theory itself (Biermann and Harsch, 2017). First, some researchers have critiqued Pfeffer and Salancik for merging the concepts of resource dependence levels and balance into a somewhat ambiguous term: interdependence. Additionally, RDT is fundamentally functionalist, characterized by rational actors pursuing utility maximization, which differs from institutionalism (Hatch, 1997). This perspective emphasizes the quantifiable aspects of the environment while restraining the societal values and norms that influence organizations. RDT also adopts an extremely agential viewpoint, suggesting that businesses do not only acclimatize to environmental limitations but also vigorously shape and change their environments (Huxham & Beech, 2010). Scholars like Mizruchi and Yoo (2002) have noted a lack of emphasis on inter-organizational power dynamics in current RDT studies.

Influenced by Selznick's (1949) initial emphasis on cooperation, RDT presupposes more collective relationships between corporations compared to theories concerning intra-organizational forces (Huxham and Beech, 2010; Katila et al., 2008; Casciaro and Piskorski, 2005). Research on interorganizational relations rarely addresses disruptive or opportunistic strategies (Benson, 1975; Katila et al., 2008). The literature, overall, indicates that RDT ought to place greater emphasis on the operational environment, networks, and inter-organizational power dynamics, while also utilizing a richer definition of resource dependence (Biermann and Harsch, 2017).

RDT conceptualizes firms as operating within open systems, requiring the exchange and acquisition of certain resources to ensure survival (Terjesen et al., 2009). The performance of a firm is contingent upon the human and social capital contributed by its board of directors (Hillman & Dalziel, 2003; Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978). Consequently, BD can enhance a firm's capacity to access various resources, including knowledge, networks, reputations, and information. Therefore, RDT suggests that a business can attain power over essential external resources needed for executing its strategy, thereby facilitating the internal development of extra resources. By recruiting board members with expertise pertinent to the firm's dependencies, organizations can reduce uncertainty. Furthermore, the theory posits that an increase in board size and diversity can strengthen the connection between firms and their external environments (Goodstein, Gautam, & Boeker, 1994; Pfeffer, 1973). Theorists argue that BD is crucial for maintaining significant resources, such as the human capital of board members, providing advice and counsel, and establishing channels for communication and legitimacy (Hillman & Dalziel, 2003; Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003). Therefore, it is advisable for firms to assemble boards composed of people with diverse know-how in applicable areas, that can augment the company's legitimacy and status (Sealy, 2010).

2.4.2 Agency Theory

With the rise of contemporary corporations, a distinct separation arose among ownership, management, and control of wealth (Davis et al., 1997). This resulted to the growth of agency relationships, where individuals with interests needed to delegate policymaking power to others (Schulze et al., 2001). Agency theory is known to be the earliest and most lengthily exploited theoretical framework in corporate governance (Daily, Dalton, & Canella, 2003). A key concern in corporate governance is the effective safeguarding of shareholders' interests. Central to agency theory is the agency problem and its potential solutions (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The agency model is one of the initial theories in management and economics literature. Specifically, "agency theory" addresses the challenges that arise when owners and managers are distinct entities within a company (Panda and Leepsa, 2017). It stresses the need to address this problem. According to Panda and Leepsa (2017), the theory suggests implementing various governance mechanisms to monitor the actions of agents in companies with multiple owners. AGT encompasses the relationship between two parties: the agent, who works or makes decisions on behalf of someone else, and the principal, who hires the agent for a specific purpose.

AGT posits that shareholders (referred to as principals) delegate the control of a firm to managers (known as agents). This arrangement, however, creates a potential risk that agents may prioritize their own interests at the expense of the principals. To address this concern, managers have developed agency theories to understand and mitigate these possible opportunistic behaviors (Williamson, 1975; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The theory focuses on scenarios where agents may favor their interests over those of their clients, with the primary

goal of ensuring that agents act in the best interests of the principals they represent. Agency theory incorporates both financial and behavioral viewpoints on corporate governance (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The financial viewpoint assumes that financial rationality drives the behavior of directors and emphasizes the importance of formal structures and systems in aligning the interests of owners and directors (Zhang et al., 2020).

Agency theory is founded on a model in which cogent individuals seek to maximize their individual utility (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Both agents and principals strive to achieve the highest possible utility at the lowest cost. Therefore, when faced with two substitutes, either the agent or the principal will select the option that enhances their individual benefit (Shahrier et al., 2019).

Consequently, agency theory posits that managers in modern organizations pursue their own interests, leading to limited rationality and risk aversion (Quigley et al., 2020). This relationship incurs costs necessary to ensure that agents make optimal decisions from the perspective of the principals (de Morais et al., 2021). Discrepancies between the decisions made by agents and the expectations of principals are commonplace (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), with information asymmetry being a significant contributor to agency issues (Mio et al., 2020). In practice, it is likely that agents and principals have differing interests and utility options. Eisenhardt (1989) identified two models within AGT: the positivist agency model and the principal-agent model. Both models entail a contractual relationship between the principal and the agent; however, the principal-agent model is more quantitative. This model delineates two parties: the principal, who is profit-driven and risk-neutral, and the agent, who is risk-averse and seeks to maximize rents. Positive agency theory examines the causes and costs associated with agency problems (Panda and Leepsa, 2017). The theory proposes two main propositions: first, if contract outcomes are incentive-based, agents will act in the interests of the principals; second, principals will impose discipline on agents' actions if they possess information about those agents (Panda & Leepsa, 2017).

Perrow (1986) criticized positive agency researchers for concentrating solely on the agent's viewpoint within the 'principal-agent problem,' making a case that this perspective neglects the possibility that issues could arise from the principal's side as well. He noted that the theory does not consider the potential for principals to deceive, shirk responsibilities, or exploit their agents. Critics such as "Wiseman and Gomez-Mejia (1998), Sanders and Carpenter (2003), and Pepper and Gore (2012)" have raised various objections to positive agency theory. In response, they have proposed an alternative framework known as behavioral agency theory, which suggests that old AGT mainly addresses the battle between principals and agents, the costs of agency, and the necessity of realigning the interests of both parties to mitigate agency problems (Panda and Leepsa, 2017).

Behavioral agency theorists advocate for changes in agent motivation, risk aversion, time preference, and fair compensation, arguing that agents are the primary focus in the principal-agent relationship and that their capabilities, motivations, and optimal opportunities significantly influence their performance (Panda and Leepsa, 2017). Given that sociologists and psychologists have highlighted flaws within agency theory, its claims should not be accepted uncritically. Nonetheless, it provides insights into relationships where individuals have conflicting goals, which can be better managed through appropriate supervision and a well-structured compensation system (de Morais et al., 2021).

In the framework of AGT, one of the board of directors' crucial roles is to oversee and mitigate managers' self-serving behaviors, thereby lowering agency costs associated with the separation of ownership and control (Carter et al., 2003). While agency theory does not directly predict how board characteristics impact FP (Carter et al., 2003; Smith et al., 2005), it does illuminate the additional value brought by female board members, which facilitates hypotheses regarding the effects of BGD on firms' economic outcomes.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

The study on the basis of the reviewed empirical studies (for example Andoh et al., 2023; Xie et al., 2024) and Resource Dependency Theory developed a conceptual framework as a guide to the study as shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework
Source: Resource Dependency Theory

From Figure 2.1, there is a direct relationship between gender diversity and financial performance and financial performance in this study is measured as return on equity. However, aside from gender, diversity, other factors such as firm size, firm growth, interest cover and tangibility affect return on asset, and these variables are called control variables in this study. Also, the relationship between gender diversity and return on equity is moderated by ownership concentration and firm size as shown in dotted line in Figure 2.1.

The study observed that much research has been carried out on the relationship between board gender diversity and financial performance. These studies have produced mixed findings where some show positive relationship, negative relationship, no significant relationship and even non-linear relationship. However, the study identified most of the study were not carried in the manufacturing firms listed on Ghana Stock Exchange. Manufacturing is very important for job creation and real gross domestic product growth in Ghana; hence, many studies need to be carried out on the study o understand how gender diversity influences financial performance among the firms. Moreover, almost all the studies reviewed considered direct relationship between board gender diversity and financial performance. However, Resource Dependency Theory and Agency Theory acknowledge that the relationship between board gender diversity and financial performance is not straight forward, but the relationship can be influenced by many factors, such as ownership concentration and firm size. This, therefore, shows a methodological gap in literature. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of board gender diversity on financial performance, using ownership concentration and firm size as moderators, in the context of manufacturing firms in Ghana. Based on the literature review and the theories reviewed in this study, the study hypothesizes as follows.

1. **H_0** : Board gender diversity does not have a statistically significant effect on the performance of manufacturing firms in Ghana.
 H_1 : Board gender diversity has a statistically significant effect on the performance of manufacturing firms in Ghana.
2. **H_0** : There is no statistically significant moderating role for ownership concentration in the relationship between board gender diversity and the performance of manufacturing firms in Ghana.
 H_1 : Ownership concentration plays a statistically significant moderating role in the relationship between board gender diversity and the performance of manufacturing firms in Ghana.
3. **H_0** : Firm size does not have a statistically significant moderating role in the relationship between board gender diversity and the performance of manufacturing firms in Ghana.
 H_1 : Firm size has a statistically significant moderating role in the relationship between board gender diversity and the performance of manufacturing firms in Ghana.

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The current research study employed an explanatory design that aligns with the quantitative methodology to ascertain the effect of GD on FP. Saïd and Alsultanny (2019) argued that explanatory research allows for the application of a certain type of study technique to look into the relationships between variables and offer an explanation for why or how certain occurrences happen. Similar to this study, explanatory research is useful for assessing hypotheses for model estimations since it seeks to show causal relationships between variables (Murphy, 2017).

Shukla and Sudhir Kumar Shukla (2023) assert that researchers conduct explanatory research to enhance their understanding of the phenomenon and delve deeper into the study subject. The results of explanatory studies may provide an improved understanding of the elements that bring about to certain events, which may assist in shaping future research or policy choices. Explanatory studies come in a variety of forms, each with a distinct methodology and objective. For example, one type of study can use correlational research, which tests one or more variables to see how they affect others (Murphy, 2017). However, the explanatory design is without limitations. Firstly, the explanatory design struggles with establishing causality, that is, distinctively helping to know or understand which variable causes the other. However, despite this limitation, explanatory design is mostly used in studies whose focus is on establishing impact of a variable on another (Murphy, 2017).

3.2 Study Population

A collection of people or units who participate in research or statistical analysis is known as the study population. The population under study includes creatures other than humans. It is a collection of traits connected through various means. Items, entities, measures, or anything else that fits into a quality category might be among them (Arias-Gómez et al., 2016). Palm et al. (2016) define the target population as all individuals and/or objects significant to the research, from which we will select sample responders. According to Arias-Gómez et al. (2016), the study population consists of all relevant items that fall within the defined geographic and contextual constraints. Therefore, a population is an assortment of characteristics from which scientists try to draw inferences.

The unit analysis of the current work encompasses all non-financial institutions listed on the GSE market. Among the listed institutions, the study on manufacturing companies comprises Aluworks Limited, Guinness Ghana Breweries Plc, Camelot Ghana Limited, Benso Oil Palm Plantation Limited, Dennex Aryton Starwin PLC, Unilever Ghana PLC, Sam Wood Ltd, Samba Foods Ltd, Fan Milk Limited, and Kasapreko Company Ltd. The study considered manufacturing companies because the manufacturing sector has traditionally been male dominated, with gender roles and norms deeply ingrained. Therefore, studying gender diversity in this sector helped to underscore how this norm has evolved over time and how this evolution is impacting the performance of the companies.

The study employed a non-probability method known as the conventional sampling technique. The study used a purposive sampling approach to select the companies. The study purposively sampled manufacturing companies (Aluworks Limited, Guinness Ghana Breweries Plc, Camelot Ghana Limited, Benso Oil Palm Plantation Limited, Dennex Aryton Starwin PLC, Unilever Ghana PLC, Sam Wood Ltd, Samba Foods Ltd, Fan Milk Limited, and Kasapreko Company Ltd) that have traded on the GSE for at least 10 years. The study considered these companies or firms because they demonstrate stability and resilience and have available management reports, aside from audited financial reports, making data accessibility easier. The study further considered these firms over the period (2014-2023) because, these firms are consistently listed on Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE); hence, accessing data from them was not difficulty.

3.3 Study Variables

This study classified the study variables into three categories: “dependent variables, independent variables, and control variables”.

$$i=1$$

Based on equation 1, the study specified the effect of board gender diversity on return on equity and return on asset with the control variables as shown in Equation 2.

$$ROE_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 BGD_{i,t} + \alpha_2 FIRMZ_{i,t} + \alpha_3 TANG_{i,t} + \alpha_4 INTCOV_{i,t} + \alpha_5 FIRMG_{i,t} + f_i + t_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots Egn 2$$

Where ROE is return on equity, BGD is board gender diversity, FIRMZ is firm size, TNAG is tangibility, INTCOV is interest cover, and FIRMG is firm growth. Research has shown that firm size positively impacts the profitability of manufacturing companies (see Joecks et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2014; Kç and Kuzey, 2016). In contrast, other studies, such as Tharu and Shrestha (2019), found no significant relationship between bank size and profitability, indicating that the effect of size on profitability in the banking sector remains ambiguous. Additionally, there is a notable relationship between asset tangibility and profitability (Kamasak, 2017). Interest coverage is identified as a significant factor influencing a firm's profitability. Furthermore, f_i and t_i represent time-invariant unobservable effects specific to manufacturing firms and time-fixed effects, respectively, while $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ denotes the error term. Moreover, the extent to which BGD affects FP depends on several factors. Theoretically, ownership concentration and firm size influence the impact of BGD on FP. For example, few shareholders own a large proportion of manufacturing firms; they often exert significant influence over the board's decisions. This can lead to a focus on short term gains or personal interests rather than long-term value creation. However, in manufacturing firms with more dispersed ownership, decision-making might be more balanced, with potentially more emphasis on governance practices and stakeholder interests. Therefore, the study estimated the moderating role of ownership concentration and firm size in the relationship between board gender diversity and return on equity as shown in Equation 3 and Equation 4.

$$ROE_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 BGD_{i,t} + \beta_2 OWNC_{i,t} + \beta_3 BGD * OWNC_{i,t} + \beta_4 FIRMZ_{i,t} + \beta_5 TANG_{i,t} + \beta_6 INTCOV_{i,t} + \beta_7 FIRMG_{i,t} + f_i + t_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots Egn 3$$

$$ROE_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 BGD_{i,t} + \beta_2 BGD * FIRMZ_{i,t} + \beta_3 FIRMZ_{i,t} + \beta_4 TANG_{i,t} + \beta_5 INTCOV_{i,t} + \beta_6 FIRMG_{i,t} + f_i + t_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots Egn 4$$

Where, BGD*OWNC is the interaction between board gender diversity and ownership concentration. Also, BGD*FIRMZ is the interaction between board gender diversity and firm size.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 4.1: Summary Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
FIRMSZ	100	16.21587	.6463604	14.95238	17.45628
firmgrowth	100	10.06285	16.04808	-1.78125	120.8488
TANG	100	.3206388	.150384	.0772802	.6034672
intcov	100	16.14194	.6815321	14.84727	17.78503
ROE	100	.2873493	.2325383	.0299329	.9511746

According to Table 4.1, manufacturing firms listed on the GSE have average firm sizes of 16.2 over the period of 2014–2023, with min and max outputs of 14.9 and 17.5, respectively. Furthermore, the listed manufacturing firms on the GSE experienced an average firm growth of 10.1, with a minimum growth of -1.8 and a maximum growth of 120.8. Also in Table 4.1, the tangibility of the manufacturing firms' GSE had an average value of 0.3. However, tangibility of firms within the period 2014-2023 had a min value of 0.8 and a max value of 0.6. In Table 4.1, interest cover for manufacturing firms within the period 2014-2023 had an average value of 16.1. Also, the interest level of the firms had min and max values of 14.8 and 17.8, respectively. Finally, the manufacturing firms had an average return on equity of 0.3 but had min and max values of 0.3 and 0.1, respectively.

The study analyzed gender diversity in manufacturing firms listed on GSE over the period 2014–2023, using the line graph below.

Figure 4.1: Analysis of Gender Diversity over 2014-2023

From Figure 4.1, the gender diversity of manufacturing firms has been increasing over the period 2014–2023, indicating that manufacturing firms in Ghana have been increasing the number of female staff, though the number of males in these companies is still higher. For example, in 2014, the GD was 0.31, but the figure increased to 0.45 in 2023, presenting a 45.16% increase. Within the period, that is, 2014-2023, the mean GD is 0.369, suggesting that, on average, for every 10 staff, there are 4 females and 6 males.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The study used a 5%-adjusted Bonferroni significance level to analyze the pairwise correlation. The essence of the correlation analysis was to show the nature and degree of relationship among the study variables.

Table 4.2: Pairwise Correlation

	ROE	GenderDive~y	FIRMSZ	firmgr~h	TANG	intcov
						1.0000
ROE						
GenderDive~y	0.1465	1.0000				
FIRMSZ	-0.0298	0.1338	1.0000			
firmgrowth	0.1197	0.0719	0.1345	1.0000		
TANG	0.4751*	0.2058	-0.0329	-0.1631	1.0000	
intcov	-0.4334*	-0.1080	0.5789*	0.1495	-0.5684*	1.0000

According to Table 4.2, firm performance (ROE) has a positive relationship with gender diversity. However, the relationship is not statistically significant, indicating that there is no significant positive relationship between gender diversity and ROE. Also, ROE and firm growth have a positive relationship, but it is not statistically significant. However, return on equity and tangibility have a significant positive relationship. This suggests that a rise in tangibility significantly increases return on equity. On the other hand, a fall in tangibility significantly reduces return on equity. Moreover, return on equity and interest cover have a significant negative relationship. This implies that a rise in interest cover significantly reduces return on equity. On the other hand, a reduction in interest cover significantly improves return on equity.

Also, a closer look at the relationship among the independent variables suggests that they are not very strongly correlated. For example, the relationship between GD and firm size, GD and firm growth, GD and tangibility, and gender diversity and interest cover was 0.338, 0.0719, 0.2058, and 0.1080, respectively. Also, the relationship between firm size and firm growth, firm size and tangibility, and firm size and interest cover was 0.1345, -0.0329, and 0.4789, respectively. Moreover, the relationship between firm growth and tangibility was -0.1631, and the relationship between firm growth and interest cover was 0.1495. Finally, the relationship between tangibility and interest cover was 0.4684. Clearly, the independent variables did not exhibit strong correlations with each other, indicating a low or no issue with multicollinearity.

4.3 Effect of GD on FP

Table 4.3. of the analysis focused on estimating the effect of GD on the ROE of firms listed on the GSE. The choice of model for estimation was between a fixed-effect model and a random effect model. The study used the Hausman specification test to determine the choice, and Table 4.3 displays the results.

Table 4.3: Hausman Specification Test Results

	(b) e	(B) Difference	(b-B) Std. err.	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))	fe
GenderDive~y	.6695058	.3738022	.2957035	.2271844	
FIRMSZ	.0768594	.0734383	.0034211	.0368364	
firmgrowth	.0024772	.0026571	-.0001799	.0002942	
TANG	.1592721	.2666736	-.1074015	.0970463	
intcov	-.1481589	-.1481717	.0000127	.033391	

Source: Author’s construct (2024)

b = Consistent under H0 and Ha; obtained from **xtreg**.

B = Inconsistent under Ha, efficient under H0; obtained from **xtreg**.

Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\begin{aligned} \text{chi2}(5) &= (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^{-1}](b-B) \\ &= 5.52 \end{aligned}$$

$$P \text{ rob} > \text{chi2} = 0.3561$$

From Table 4.3, the Hausman Specification test produced Chi=quare=5.52 with pvalue=0.3561. This shows that between FEM and REM, the REM was the most suitable model for the estimate. Therefore, the study used the REM based on the Hausman specificity test to estimate the effect of GD on ROE, as shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Effect of Gender Diversity on Return on Equity

ROE	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
Gender Diversity	.3738022	.3519917	1.06	0.288	-.3160888	1.063693
FIRMSZ	.0734383	.0509717	1.44	0.150	-.0264644	.1733409
Firm Growth	.0026571	.0012121	2.19	0.028*	.0002814	.0050328
Tangibility	.2666736	.1939098	1.38	0.169	-.1133827	.6467299
Interest Cover	-.1481717	.0538852	-2.75	0.006 *	-.2537847	-.0425586
Constant	1.246046	.6317309	1.97	0.049 *	.0078759	2.484216

Number of Obs.	100
Number of Groups	10
R-square : Within	0.1538
Between	0.5797
Overall	0.3163
Wald chi square (5)	26.82
P-value	0.0001*
Sigma_u	0.0847244
sigma_e	0.17997954
rho	0.18140177 (fraction of variance due to u_i)

Dependent Variable=ROE; *Significant at 5%

4.4 Effect of Gender Diversity on Firm Performance

The results in Table 4.4 show that GD does not significantly impact on equity. Therefore, the study accepts the null hypothesis that GD does not have a statistically significant impact on FP. Though GD has a positive impact (Coeff. = 0.3738; $p = 0.288$) on return on equity, the impact is not significant. Singh et al. (2008) assert that because female directors have taken distinct routes to become directors, they have distinct backgrounds and expertise. This is not consistent with Resource Dependence Theory. According to Resource Dependence theory, having gender diversity acts as a resource that help manufacturing firms to effectively manage dependencies. Gender diversity enhances decision-making processes by introducing different viewpoints, leading to more balanced and better-informed choices that can help improve financial performance of manufacturing firms. Given their nurturing responsibilities in the family, the majority of female directors had greater experience managing the house even if they were not top executives when they were recruited as board members. Furthermore, likened to their male colleagues, women often have greater domestic control over decisions like domestic sales and purchases (Phipps and Burton, 1998). According to Campbell and Minguez-Vera (2008), the appointment of female directors may thereby boost the corporate management's comprehension of the consumer markets. Furthermore, Groysberg and Bell (2013) assert that female directors are more inclined than their male colleagues to engage in philanthropy and community service, which might result in creative solutions that are pertinent to businesses' objectives. Boards with a varied range of genders are more inclined to have in-depth conversations that will improve the company's bottom line. Loyd et al. (2013) claim that well-diversified boards share a wider range of knowledge and abilities and participate in deeper conversations than homogenous boards. According to Peterson and Philpot (2007), male directors are more likely to decide based on conventional methods of problem-solving that adhere to set rules and regulations, while Mahadeo et al. (2012) contend that female directors are more probable to accept a supportive decision-making approach with less bias, particularly when competing interests are at stake. Reguera-Alvarado et al. (2017) claim that a company's financial performance improves when more women are serving as directors. Diversity on the Board of Directors and Commissioners aims to promote thorough and impartial decision-making, as decisions are based on a range of viewpoints. Rose (2007) expresses the desire for a significant increase in the representation of women on boards. In research on the effects of gender diversity on councils' business performance in Turkey, Kuzey (2016) discovered that women's roles improved the return on equity for the company. Gomez (2018) posits that while women's contributions to firm success (ROA) yield a positive but insignificant effect, their influence amplifies when evaluating performance through a shareholder-orientated metric (ROE). Faramita (2016) revealed a substantial positive association between the variable ROE and the number of women on the board of commissioners, which supports this result.

4.5 Control Variables

The study found that firm size (Coeff. = 0.0734; standard error = 0.0509; $p = 0.150$) is not statistically significant. The results are consistent with those of Adebayo (2022), who demonstrated that there is no statistically significant correlation between ROE and business size. In another study, Dogan (2013) explored the impact of business size on profitability and revealed a favorable correlation between firm size and return on equity. Akbağ and Karaduman (2012) examined the impact of business size on profitability for industrial firms listed on the ISE between 2005 and 2011. The study's findings demonstrated that business size positively impacts profitability. Khatap et al. (2011) examined the relationship between the CG and performance of 20 companies listed on the KSE. The study, which employed data from the years 2005–2009, discovered a negative and statistically not significant relationship between ROE and total assets but a positive relationship between total assets and ROA. Furthermore, Karadeniz and skenderolu (2011) have examined the factors influencing the tourist enterprises listed in ISE's ROA. The study's conclusions disclosed a positive and statistically significant association between total assets, a size indicator, and ROA. According to Gharaibeh and Bani Khaled (2020), risk, expansion, and business size all significantly increase profitability. According to Amponsah-Kwatiah and Asiamah (2020), there is a positive association between firm size and ROA and ROE in Ghanaian listed manufacturing firms. Meanwhile, Stierwald (2010) suggests that firm size positively affects profitability in non-manufacturing US firms and large Australian firms. Also, tangibility (Coeff. = 0.2667; standard error = 0.1939; $p = 0.169$) has no statistically significant impact on ROE. Gharaibeh and Bani Khaled (2020) looked into the variables that affected 46 Jordanian listed service businesses' profitability between 2014 and 2018. The findings show that tangible assets and leverage have a significant and opposite impact on profitability. Irungu et al. (2018) disclosed a positive and significant correlation between asset tangibility and the financial performance of both financial and nonfinancial enterprises. The study concluded that asset tangibility positively and significantly impacts the financial performance of listed firms on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. Koksall et al. (2013) looked at the variables influencing Turkey's capital structure decisions. They replaced the term "asset type" with "tangibility." Their findings suggest that tangibility plays a major role in determining long-term leverage (a positive link), but it has no bearing on short-term leverage. Investments in fixed assets have a significant and favorable statistical influence on the banking industry's profitability, according to Olatunji et al. (2014). Martina (2015) looked into how Croatian small and medium-sized businesses' financial structures and tangible assets related to one another. All years of observation showed a positive and statistically significant association between tangible assets and long-term leverage. The Okwo et al. (2012) study assessed the impact of a company's fixed asset investment on its operational profit margin. The study found a positive relationship between fixed asset investment and operating profit, but not statistically significant.

However, firm growth (Coeff. =0.0027; Std Error=0.0012; $p=0.028$) has a statistically significant positive impact on return on equity. According to the results, a 1% increase in firm growth significantly increases the ROE by 0.003%. On the other hand, a 1% decrease in firm growth significantly decreases return on equity by 0.003%. Ubesie and Okeke (2013) examined the effect of company growth indicators on business value in Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Analysis reveals that total assets, company age, and personnel count statistically positively impact the firm's net asset value, while total sales significantly negatively impact it. Simanullang et al. (2021) demonstrated in another study that business valuation positively affects return on equity.

Moreover, interest cover (Coeff. =0.1481; Std Error= 0.0534; p=0.006) has statistically significant negative impact on ROE. According to the results, a 1% increase in interest coverage significantly reduces the return on equity by 14.8%. Also, a 1% decrease in interest cover significantly increases ROE by 14.8%. The interest cover ratio calculates how well a corporation can use its earnings from operations to pay interest. It shows the amount of buffer the business has to cover its set obligation of paying interest on its debt. You can use the ratio as a proxy for the company's ability to settle its debts and sustain its operations. Interest coverage plays a crucial role in determining a company's creditworthiness since the rating indicates the company's ability to make repayments (Kim et al., 2013). In order to pay interest, the business must make enough money. A high interest coverage ratio increases a company's likelihood of being able to pay its debts (Palomino et al., 2019). The degree of gearing, the cost of borrowings, and the profitability of the firm all affect the capacity of the corporation to pay its interest costs. Interest coverage has a favorable and statistically significant impact on ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q, according to research by Arhinful et al. (2023). The study's results demonstrated that cash coverage positively and statistically significantly impacts ROE.

4.6 Moderating Role of Ownership in the Relationship Between GD and ROE

This section of the analysis focused on the moderating role of ownership, which was measured as the concentration of ownership in the relationship between GD and return on equity. Table 4.5 displays the estimated results from REM.

Table 4.5: Moderating Role of Ownership in the Relationship BGD and ROE

Variables	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
Gender Diversity	.047232	.4507474	0.10	0.917	-.8362165	.9306806
Ownership Concentration	.2561577	.2259455	1.13	0.257	-.1866874	.6990029
Ownership Concentration *Gender Diversity	-.2201107	.6676375	-0.33	0.742	-1.528656	1.088435
Firm Size	.0691165	.0488965	1.41	0.158	-.0267188	.1649519
Firm growth	.003334	.0011452	2.91	0.004*	.0010894	.0055786
Tangibility	.4350858	.2048629	2.12	0.034*	.0335619	.8366097
Interest Cover	-.1516426	.0514309	-2.95	0.003 *	-.2524453	-.0508399
Constant	1.342321	.5935591	2.26	0.024*	.178967	2.505676
Number of Observation	100					
Number of Groups	10					
R-square: Within	0.2721					
Between	0.7336					
Overall	0.4450					
Wald Chi-Square (7)	45.16					
P-value	0.0000*					
Sigma_u	0.0957857					
sigma_e	0.16933288					
rho	0.24241104	(fraction of variance due to u _i)				

Dependent Variable: ROE: *Significant at 5%

From Table 4.5, ownership concentration (Coeff. =0.256; Std Error=0.226; p=0.257) does not have a statistically significant impact on ROE. Also, the interaction of ownership concentration and gender diversity (Coeff. =-0.2201; Std Error=0.668; p=0.742) has a negative impact on ROE. However, the impact is not statistically significant. Therefore, the study accepts the null hypothesis that ownership concentration does not significantly moderate the relationship between GD and the ROE of firms listed on the GSE. Affan, Rosidiand, and Purwanti (2017) assert that the allocation of capital, votes, and equity owners' identities dictate the ownership structure. Thus, a company's ownership structure has a significant impact on its financial success. Moreover, Dou, Hope, Thomas, and Zou (2018) examined the impact of ownership structure on value during the region's financial crisis using a sample of 800 businesses across eight East Asian nations. In a similar vein, Abdul (2016) evaluated in his research how ownership structure affected the NSE-listed businesses' financial performance. The first result demonstrated a strong inverse relationship between institutional ownership and the financial success of the enterprises as estimated by returns on assets. The second study showed that insider ownership and business performance had a substantial positive relationship. Using a linear regression of an accounting measure of returns, Bricker and Markarian (2015) demonstrated the endogeneity of the ownership structure of significant US firms.

The results go counter to Mandaci and Gumus's (2021) findings, which showed that ownership concentration significantly improves company performance. Ajao and Ejokhuma look at the impact of ownership concentration on manufacturing companies' financial performance in another study. Contrary to the study's conclusions, the actual data showed that the concentrations of government, block, and institutional ownership all had a substantial impact (direct and inverse) on the performance measures (ROA, TOBIN Q). Robust analysis, however, also showed that the concentration of government ownership had a mostly detrimental impact on the financial performance of the corresponding companies. Consistent with the study's findings, the majority of manufacturing businesses exhibit a generally positive coefficient of block ownership concentration, but the institutional ownership concentration coefficient is primarily negative. Mudi (2017) looks into how the rights structure affects the NSE-quoted companies' profitability. According to the research, acquiring rights has a significant impact on a company's profitability. Ogaluzor (2019) verified a statistically significant negative correlation between the purchase of rights and profitability.

4.7 Moderating Role of Firm Size in the Relationship Between BGD and ROE

This part of the analysis considered the moderating role of ownership, measured as concentration of ownership in the relationship between gender diversity and return on equity. The results as estimated by REM are shown in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Moderating Role of Firm Size in the Relationship Between BGD and ROE

Study Variables	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
Gender Diversity	.9336419	8.650675	0.11	0.914	-16.02137	17.88865
Firm Size*Gender	-.0335642	.5455476	-0.06	0.951	-1.102818	1.035689
Diversity						
Firm Size	.0858618	.2039289	0.42	0.674	-.3138314	.485555
Firm Growth	.0026466	.0012226	2.16	0.030	.0002504	.0050428
Tangibility	.2559111	.1961622	1.30	0.192	-.1285597	.6403819
Interest Cover	-.1480385	.0548328	-2.70	0.007	-.2555089	-.0405681
Constant	1.040775	3.254305	0.32	0.749	-5.337546	7.419097
Number of Observation	100					

Number of Groups	10
R-Square: Within	0.1554
Between	0.5698
Overall	0.3138
Wald Chi-Square (6)	25.51
P-value	0.0003
Sigma_u	0.09308107
sigma_e	0.18102086
rho	0.20911256 (fraction of variance due to u i)

From Table 4.6, the interaction of firm size and gender diversity (Coeff. =-0.0336; Std Error=0.5455; p=0.951) has a negative impact on ROE. However, the impact is not statistically significant. Therefore, the study confirms the null hypothesis that firm size does not significantly moderate the relationship between GD and return on equity of firms listed on GSE. The results of Liu et al.'s (2014) investigation of the impact of GD on boards on the performance of Chinese listed companies between 1999 and 2011 indicated a strong and favourable correlation between BGD and company performance. Based on data from the Netherlands and Denmark, Marinova et al. (2016) studied the relationship between GD on boards and business performance to determine whether it improves performance. According to Korkmaz and Kuzey (2016), the boards of these Turkish companies are predominately male, and the presence of female directors is favorably correlated with the financial success of the companies, as determined by the return on equity, the return on assets, and the return on sales. Research has demonstrated that GD significantly enhances financial performance (Brahma et al., 2021). But when three or more women are nominated to the board, as opposed to fewer, the favorable impact on financial performance becomes clear-cut and quite significant. Vieito's (2013) research indicates that the CEO's gender does not significantly impact a company's success on average. More specifically, there is no discernible difference in stock return between CEOs who are male or female and those who are female in terms of the business risk level. According to Amponsah-Kwatiah and Asiamah (2020), there is a positive correlation between firm size and ROA and ROE in Ghanaian listed manufacturing firms. Meanwhile, Stierwald (2010) suggests that firm size positively affects profitability in non-manufacturing US firms and large Australian firms.

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that gender diversity does not have a significant impact on ROE. While ROE and firm growth demonstrate a positive relationship, this relationship is not statistically significant. A significant positive relationship is observed between ROE and tangibility, while ROE and interest cover show a significant negative relationship. Additionally, firm size and tangibility do not have statistically significant impacts on ROE, whereas firm growth and interest exhibit statistically significant positive impacts on ROE. Furthermore, ownership concentration does not have a statistically significant effect on ROE, and its interaction with gender diversity yields a negative but statistically insignificant impact on ROE. Similarly, the interaction between firm size and gender diversity shows a negative but statistically insignificant effect on ROE.

This study offers some implications. First, given the significant role of gender diversity in enhancing corporate performance, it is recommended that management and regulatory bodies adopt the principles of critical mass theory. Ensuring a substantial representation of women on corporate boards can enhance the positive impact of diverse perspectives. However, it is crucial

to prioritize appointments based on competencies and qualifications rather than familial connections, fostering a board that benefits from both diversity and expertise. Second, companies operating in environments with weak corporate governance and challenging macroeconomic conditions can improve survival and financial performance by adopting robust internal governance structures. Tailoring governance models to the specific challenges within their operating environment may help mitigate systemic risks and contribute to stronger financial outcomes. Third, Ghanaian firms considering expansion beyond domestic markets could benefit from either listing on an international stock exchange or appointing foreign board members. The strategic addition of a foreign board member can provide long-term value and global perspectives, often at a lower cost than cross-listing. This approach serves as an affordable alternative for firms hesitant about cross-listing or as a complementary strategy for those already internationally listed, enhancing cross-border influence and fostering growth. Fourth, the manufacturing firms should set a clear diversity target and goals. The firms should publicly commit to the set target and ensure that the right number of females are well represented on the board within a given time-period. Finally, the firms should also establish a female talent pipeline by actively identifying and mentoring high-potential female leaders within the firms. The firms can create development programs and provide leadership training to prepare women for board-level positions.

This study is not without its limitation. The primary limitation of this study was the small sample size, due to the limited number of manufacturing firms listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange. This constraint means that the firms included may not accurately represent the broader population of manufacturing firms in Ghana. Additionally, the exclusive reliance on quantitative data limited the study's ability to capture insights into the impact of board gender diversity (BGD) on firm performance from the perspectives of Ghanaian manufacturing firms. Further research could extend the sample to include all sectors on the stock exchange and use mixed method strategy to gain richer data.

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